

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable D6.8

Ecosystem building and service incubator activities II

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Short Description:
The LandSense Ecosystem building and service incubator activities II provides insights into the consortium activities in respect to ecosystem building. Activities undertaken, and stakeholders engaged in the second half of the project are elaborated in detail, with attention given to second LandSense Innovation Challenge organized as the online incubator event. This deliverable represents the update of the D6.3 Ecosystem building and services incubator I.
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Executive Summary

LandSense is one of four Horizon 2020 projects funded under the SC5-17-2015 - *Demonstrating the concept of 'Citizen Observatories'* call. The project started on 1st of September 2016 and aims to build a far-reaching citizen observatory for Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) monitoring that will also function as a technology innovation marketplace. Led by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), 18 partners from 9 European countries have teamed up to mobilize and deliver an observatory and innovation marketplace that combines the powers of Citizen Science (CS) and Earth Observation (EO) for LULC monitoring.

D6.8 Ecosystem building and services incubator II represents the update of the D6.3 Ecosystem building and services incubator I. As such, it reports the activities undertaken in the second half of the project with the goal of disseminating innovative elements within the LandSense project, facilitating collaboration, engaging identified stakeholders to understand and to use the LandSense results for their own interests/organization and ultimately providing feedback for more effective exploitation potential of the project results.

Throughout the second half of the project consortium partners carried out many ecosystem building activities, actions and events, according to the time plan. Printable or digital informational dissemination material was distributed at each of the mentioned events. These actions followed the overall dissemination strategy.

1. Introduction

LandSense is an EU-funded project dedicated towards building an innovative citizen observatory in the field of LULC, by collecting data both actively (through citizens) and passively (from authoritative, open access, and other citizen-based initiatives) and integrating it into an open platform that provides valuable quality-assured in-situ data for SMEs, larger businesses, government agencies, NGOs and researchers to use. A key component of the LandSense Citizen Observatory is the LandSense engagement platform that facilitates innovative environmental monitoring by connecting communities, LandSense core services, data resources and demonstration cases. To this end, the project aims to uncover the potential of citizen science and earth observation to improve our environmental knowledge base, which includes the production of accurate information on land use, land cover (LULC) and changes to the landscape over time.

LandSense services are designed to contribute to LULC monitoring within three major themes, urban landscape dynamics, agricultural land use, and forestry and habitat. For example, the innovative tools provide farmers with information on vegetation health status from remotely sensed EO data as an incentive to share data on crops grown, crop phenological information (e.g. emergence and flowering), management information (e.g. dates of planting and harvest as well as nutrient use and application), occurrence of pests and diseases and impact of extreme weather.

This deliverable presents the activities undertaken with the respect to LandSense ecosystem building. Ecosystem building activities are crucial in development of project's outputs and the position in the earth observation value chain, ultimately contributing to strengthening the post project exploitation opportunities. The deliverable represents an update of D6.3 Ecosystem building and service incubator activities I.

In particular, the report is structured into 5 distinct sections:

- **Section 1** provides introductory information with respect to the LandSense project and the context in which the current report has been elaborated.
- **Section 2** outlines the scope, objectives and the importance of Ecosystem building.
- **Section 3** presents LandSense partners corresponding activities, engagement and achievements in respect to Ecosystem building.
- **Section 4** provides overview of further activities and concluding remarks.

Finally, the **Annex** of the report provides an overview of the LandSense documents used in its Ecosystem building activities.

2. Scope and Objectives

The overarching objective of this deliverable is to summarize the LandSense consortium's activities and achievements in the second half of the project towards creating a valuable ecosystem of stakeholders who support further uptake and exploitation of the project results within the broad Earth Observation ecosystem in Europe.

More specifically, the objectives of LandSense ecosystem building is the following:

- To better understand the different ways EO stakeholders are currently engaged in LULC activities within the EO Ecosystem as well as the extent of their engagement.
- To capture the geographical scope of the online collaborations for innovation within LandSense domains and evaluate the willingness of relevant stakeholders to establish new or enhance their existing online collaborations for innovation
- To involve relevant EO stakeholders in LandSense ecosystem with the goal of expanding its userbase; involve as many active players in iterative lean development process and thus further develop LandSense services; bring on new partners who will attach their own services and products to the LandSense offerings; to engage stakeholders through open innovation to build on LandSense offerings
- To identify the main barriers that appear to be preventing LandSense from expanding its innovation activities as well as key success factors that may facilitate its adoption to their business and innovation processes.
- To gain insights into the perceived knowledge, skills, tools and/or support that stakeholders require in order to successfully capitalise on LandSense innovation.

The scope of the LandSense ecosystem building is to include SMEs from across the earth observation value chain and its supporting industries (i.e. from end-users including research organizations, technology firms, enterprises, data providers/data seekers, public bodies, to citizens as a whole.) as well as representatives of innovation intermediaries and SME support networks across Europe. Interconnections and interdependencies created through LandSense incubator activities provide interested organizations with knowledge of how to use LandSense outcomes for their own interests.

3. LandSense Ecosystem Building Activities

3.1 Ecosystem Incubator Events

Two Ecosystem incubator events / Challenges were organised to engage citizen science community and other EO actors with LandSense project and platform. The events were designed to target EO involved individuals, web-entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs coming from all participating Horizon 2020 countries. The Challenges invited participants to present innovative IT ideas addressing at least one of the three LandSense domains: Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, and Forest & Habitat Monitoring. The Challenges focused on using data streams coming from the LandSense Citizen Observatory, the Sentinel Hub Service or other relevant EO data sources to design novel LULC solutions for a range of applications within the selected domains.

The First LandSense Innovation Challenge took place during the Second International ECSA Conference 2018 in Geneva on 3 June 2018. This event was based on a Hackathon concept, supported knowledge sharing through a one-day event where participants present and share their technical capabilities, innovation and creativity. The details related to the Challenge organisation and achievements were presented in D6.3 Ecosystem building and services incubator I.

The Second LandSense Innovation Challenge was initially scheduled for May 27th, 2020 as a side event during the Third International ECSA Conference 2020 in Trieste. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the conference and Challenge were rescheduled for September, where the Challenge took place on 11 September 2020 as an online event. The event shared the same objectives as the First LandSense Innovation Challenge:

- Promotion of the best pitch presentations that could have a clear business impact
- Awareness creation about the LandSense project objectives and outcomes
- Fostering the community spirit within the LandSense Citizen Observatory

Each of the finalists received:

- Business coaching and mentorship services before the Challenge (the webinar “How to pitch your idea” was organized by INOSENS in order to train the finalists to professionally present their ideas by preparing adequate content of their presentation slides as well as their oral presentations)
- Matchmaking and networking opportunities with leading experts in EO and citizen science engaged in the LandSense project and ECSA 2020 Conference
- Promotional services by LandSense (via the project communication and dissemination channels)
- Presentation about the LandSense project and LandSense Engagement Platform

The three teams with the best pitches received following prizes:

1st prize

- A grand prize of 2,000 EUR
- A 1-year subscription to Sentinel Hub Enterprise, worth 5,000 EUR (provided by SINERGISE)
- Online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the LandSense team

2nd prize

monitoring of community forestry on bio-physical parameters through geospatial approach; and quantifying urban development and assisting in identifying informal/illegal dealings in urban land.

During the first part of the online Challenge, three topics were presented: i) introductory session on the LandSense project and its achievements including detail presentation of the LandSense Engagement Platform and produced data-sets (presented by IIASA)¹; ii) presentation on the Landscape of Citizen Science and Citizen Observatories (presented by ECSA)² and iii) presentation on Sentinel Hub Services (presented by SINGERGISE)³. This session was an ideal opportunity for all the participants and finalists to network and exchange ideas and to boost citizen science in the environmental monitoring context. The challenge participants actively interacted during the “Q&A” session as well as via the open chat session.

The second part of the online Challenge was devoted to the evaluation of the idea pitches, which was very demanding as each team had 10 minutes for their pitch with a 10-minute Q&A. The idea was to give the participants a sense of the Venture Capital evaluation process and prepare them for the market. After each unique pitch, the LandSense jury members made sure their line of questioning was thorough. The LandSense jury members were composed of LandSense consortium partners from IIASA, SINGERGISE, ECSA and INOSENS.

Figure 2 The LandSense Innovation Challenge poster

¹ This presentation can be assessed through this [link](#).

² This presentation can be assessed through this [link](#).

³ This presentation can be assessed through this [link](#).

Finalists Pitch Summaries:

Presentation 1

Organization: AeroEye Solutions Pvt Ltd (Zimbabwe)
Team: Ali Freeman, Reason Mlambo, Edward Gezi and Victor Mutoma
Idea Name: iShow Tenure – iST
LandSense domain: Urban Landscape Dynamics

Pitch Summary:

AeroEye Solutions proposes a digital platform to aid in quantifying urban development and assisting in identifying informal/illegal dealings in urban land. The platform is accessible via the internet and is hereafter referred to as iShow Tenure (iST). The iST is an intelligent system that displays land parcels that have been surveyed and approved by the Department of Surveyor General against an approved land use plan. Additionally, land use land cover change dynamics are displayed through the platform enabling citizens and planning authorities to identify any mismatches between the planned and reality on the ground. The system enables citizens to amplify their voices against unplanned development.

Figure 3 Insights from iShow Tenure – iST Presentation

Presentation 2

Organization: Independent entrepreneur (France)

Team: Ravindhiran Viswalingam and Aditya Pawar

Idea Name: iObserve app for Forest and Habitat Monitoring

LandSense domain: Forest & Habitat Monitoring.

Pitch Summary:

According to “wilderness-society.org”, most European forests consist of non-native species of plants. Does this mean forests are losing their originality? Even if it’s just an argument, but it needs our focus. Therefore, not only the monitoring of size or volume of the forests is needed but the data about the plant and animal species within it are also important so that the right action can be taken at the right time. To do this we will introduce an app called iObserve to solve this purpose and roll it out to trekkers, forest tour guides, and tourists visiting forests.

Figure 4 Insights from iObserve app for Forest and Habitat Monitoring Presentation

Presentation 3

Organization: ExCiteS (University College London’s Extreme Citizen Science research group) (UK)

Team: Marcos Moreu and ExCiteS research group

Idea Name: A satellite imagery-based mapping prototype for land use mapping by land users

LandSense domain: Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, Forest & Habitat Monitoring.

Pitch Summary:

Co-creating mapping tools and methods that allow anyone, regardless of the level of literacy, technological skills and previous mapping experience, to create and interact with digital land use maps will contribute to reducing inequality in participation; enhance the collaboration between citizens with different backgrounds, realities and land-related geographic knowledge; and ultimately help to understand how humans use the land (if at all ever possible) and ensure sustainable development for all.

Identifying the problems

Rural poverty
Lack of evidence of people-to-land relationships often contributes to insecurity of land rights, and ultimately poverty.

Climate change
Lack of local knowledge, information and data about human-land interactions reduces our capacity to ensure sustainable development for all.

It is estimated that 70% of the world’s people-to-land relationships are NOT recorded.

Open data-driven collaboration: Potential users and business model

Local knowledge. Open big land data. Information. Data. Funds.

- Research institutions
- Development agencies
- DRR bodies
- Cadastre agencies
- Geospatial companies
- ...

Specialised services (Free) | Open Source Community

Geographic local knowledge: No restrictions

Screen 1: Icon A, Icon B
Screen 2: Icon C, Icon D
4 possible combinations: A-C, A-D, B-C, B-D
Very limited knowledge can be captured

Screen 3: Alphabet A (random) positions
'Individual' combinations
'Holistic' knowledge can be captured

Optimal balance between possible combinations (combined land potential attributes) knowledge that could be captured

Challenges

- Social challenges → Social needs (understanding), ...
- Technological challenges → Appropriate technology, ...
- Security challenges → Appropriate protocols and technology, ...
- Institutional and legal challenges → Data quality and data legitimacy, ...

Figure 5 Insights from A satellite imagery-based mapping prototype for land use mapping by land users Presentation

Presentation 4

Organization: Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Novi Sad (Serbia)
Team: Minuđer Mesaroš, Imre Nagy, Dragoslav Pavić, Slobodan Marković, Tin Lukić, Biljana Basarin, Atila Bezdan, Tijana Đorđević and Miloš Ostojić
Idea Name: Geospatial platform for allergenic plant monitoring and management
LandSense domain: Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use

Pitch Summary:

Allergenic plants (e.g. common ragweed - *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*), represent a significant economic and public health problem, reducing the quality of life, productivity, increasing healthcare costs and causing losses in agricultural production. The mitigation of the aggressive and rapid spread of allergenic invasive species requires a coordinated national response, with the active participation of the government, local institutions and the public. The plan envisages the use of remote sensing-based geospatial information system as a common platform for connecting and coordinating all stakeholders, which is essential for effective and successful eradication and management

Figure 6 Insights from Geospatial platform for allergenic plant monitoring and management Presentation

Presentation 5

Organization: Kathmandu Forestry College (Nepal)
Team: Him Lal Shrestha and Deepak Kumar Shah
Idea Name: Monitoring of Community Forestry on Bio-Physical parameters through Geospatial approach
LandSense domain: Forest & Habitat Monitoring.

Pitch Summary:

After the successful participatory forest management practices in Nepal, the practice is moved to global attention and now the CF management approach is being implemented widely in the world. The 40 years of experience and well stated successful CF programme needs some sort of monitoring on different indicators such as social, governance, institutional and bio-physical aspects. The project aims to focus on the spatial and associated biophysical indicators which can be generated through Remote Sensing, GIS, and GPS technologies coupled with the IT solutions.

Market and Customers

Architecture

Technological Solutions

Forest Cover Change Validation Tool

Figure 7 Insights from Monitoring of Community Forestry on Bio-Physical parameters through Geospatial approach Presentation

Ultimately it was concluded that the Serbian team consisting of researchers and scientists from the Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad with the idea “Geospatial platform for allergenic plant monitoring and management” takes the first prize at the Second LandSense Innovation Challenge. This team received a 1-year subscription to Sentinel Hub Enterprise, worth 5,000 EUR, provided by Sinergise, online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the LandSense team and a grand prize of 2,000 EUR. The second prize went to Nepalese team consisting of researchers and scientists from Kathmandu Forestry College with the idea “Monitoring of Community Forestry on Bio-Physical parameters through Geospatial approach”. This team received a prize of 1,000 EUR and the online business coaching and mentorship services provided by LandSense team. Finally, the third prize went to Zimbabwean team consisting of EO and IT entrepreneurs and representatives of AeroEye Solutions company with the idea “iShow Tenure - iST”. This team received a prize of 500 EUR and the online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the LandSense team.

Figure 8 The Challenge winners being promoted on LandSense Facebook

3.1.1 Challenge Dissemination

The second LandSense Innovation Challenge open call lasted for one and a half months, from Jul 8th until Aug 21st, 2020. During this time, GeoVille and InoSens led the dissemination activities, with LandSense partners also sharing the prepared information through their own online channels.

GeoVille and InoSens performed the dissemination of the open call through online social networks Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, actively engaging Earth Observation, GIS, environmental and remote sensing influencers to further share the posts. In addition to well populated LandSense and ECSA internal mailing lists, EO start-up community was engaged through the GeoVille and InoSens direct contacts. Horizon2020 project and EU accelerator PARSEC Accelerator was engaged for further disseminating the news about the Challenge with its SMEs from the EO sector.

In order to promote the Challenge and to facilitate application process as well as to clarify all potential doubts about the Challenge, LandSense team organised a “LandSense Innovation Challenge webinar⁴” via Zoom platform on 11 August.

Figure 9 The Challenge webinar being promoted on LandSense Twitter

⁴ Slides from the Aug 11 - LandSense Innovation Webinar - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3979268>

According to FaceBook metrics, the main post announcing the Second LandSense Challenge reach 44,537 persons and achieved 4,865 post engagements, as can be seen in from the following figure.

Figure 10 LandSense FaceBook statistics related to post announcing LandSense Innovation Challenge

Figure 11 Earth Observation and Citizen Science actors sharing news about LandSense Innovation Challenge

Figure 12 LandSense Innovation Challenge being promoted through LandSense channels

3.1.2 Feedback on the Second LandSense Challenge Event

A short online survey was distributed among LandSense Challenge Finalists after the event. As can be seen in the following chart, the findings indicate a very positive experience related to the event organisation and its content. Moreover, the participants indicated a notable interest in future LandSense events and activities, which further indicates that such incubator events are an excellent way for LandSense to engage with its stakeholders and potential users of its services.

Figure 13 LandSense Ecosystem Building Survey Findings

Additional Testimonials from the Challenge participants

- “Thank you for successfully organizing the LandSense Competition. Such competitions help in catalyzing innovations.” – **Freemen Ali**
- “It was a wonderful experience for me. Looking forward to more such competitions in the future and thanks a lot for the feedback. It was really helpful.” – **Ravindhiran Visawalingam**
- “Thank you for especially for providing this very valuable feedback which will help us improve our work. Participating in the challenge has been a very good experience for me.” – **Marcos Moreu**
- “The challenge was a great catalyst leading towards this goal, the experience and prizes will be very valuable and useful in our further work. We very much look forward to cooperating with the LandSense team and working with SentinelHub in the future!” – **Minučer Mesaroš**

After the event, the winners of the Second LandSense Challenge were interviewed by the LandSense dissemination and communication lead (GeoVille) with the aim of sharing their positive experience with other LandSense stakeholders as well as to promote the LandSense as a unique citizen observatory and innovation marketplace for LULC. The interviews have been published on the LandSense website and promoted via its social media channels.

3.2 Notable LandSense activities aimed at Ecosystem Building

The following section highlights notable LandSense activities realised during the second half of the project where LandSense partners had an opportunity to meet with representatives of influential Earth Observation networks, policy makers, researchers, SMEs, public and other relevant stakeholders through organized workshops, conferences, hackathons and meetings. Each of the following activities has in its own regard contributed to the expand LandSense project scope and projects involvement in the Earth Observation industry. The activities have empowered the LandSense federated system to bring in partners to develop synergies among complementary service enabling the scaling-up of existing services, knowledge bases and development of novel value-added LULC products. Moreover, through such collective interaction with the involved stakeholders, this ‘power of collaboration’ will lead to the fast adoption of LandSense services and ultimately strengthen the projects ecosystem for an effective post-project exploitation.

3.2.1 EuroGEOSS Workshop: Crowdsourcing Land Use Map Validation, Switzerland

12-14 September 2018

At the EuroGEOSS Workshop in Geneva, LandSense researchers from IIASA and the University of Heidelberg hosted an interactive mapping session to showcase the power of crowdsourcing for map validations.

Using the openly available Land Cover Validation Platform (LACO-Wiki), participants collaboratively validated a land use and land cover map of Geneva, which brings together data from both earth observation (ESA’s Sentinel 2) and OpenStreetMap data streams. During this session participants gained first-

hand knowledge on how microtasks distributed to a crowd can be an efficient approach to validate maps using high resolution satellite imagery. Furthermore, degree of agreement between the contributors was presented as a means of addressing the quality and confidence of the crowd-driven approach. The session was very successful with validations of some 750 points within just 15 minutes. Participants consisted of members of the academic community, industry and representatives from the Executive Agency for SMEs.

3.2.2 LandSense at GEO WEEK 2018, Japan

29.10-02.11.2018

The GEO Week in Kyoto, Japan assembled GEO's 105 Member governments and 127 Participating Organizations in order to explore efforts and opportunities for the use of EO for the benefit of humankind, while focusing on GEO's three priority areas: the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, the Paris Climate Agreement, and the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

The LandSense Coordinator Steffen Fritz participated in a dedicated session on "Elevating Citizen Science at GEO". The meeting delved more deeply into how the GEO community can benefit from incorporating citizen science (CS) methodologies more widely. Contributors (1) discussed activities already underway to advance the established GEO work plan, (2) considered how GEO can strengthen their involvement in and support for citizen science through partnerships and emerging endeavours, and (3) discussed concrete next steps for advancing citizen science through GEO.

3.2.3 SIGMA Students from ENSAT Toulouse contribute to LandSense, France

24.10. 2018

Thirteen students from SIGMA (Geographic Sciences for Environment and Planning) at the University of Toulouse along, with their instructor David Shereen, participated in the LandSense Urban Landscape Dynamics pilot using the PAYSAGES France mobile application developed by the French National Mapping Agency (IGN France) and IIASA.

The overall goal of this pilot was to engage citizens and local authorities, as well as stakeholders involved in decision support and local planning of land monitoring processes. In particular, this pilot evaluated how citizen-contributed data complements authoritative data sources, advance current operational workflows and provide quality-assured cost-effective solutions for LULC monitoring and change detection.

The field-campaign with the SIGMA students was very successful, collecting more than 100 in-situ validations that had been used to train the change detection algorithm for automatic land use and land use change detection.

3.2.4 The Common Dissemination Booster – Citizen Observatory Group Formed

November 2018

The Common Dissemination Booster (Trust-IT Services) is a novel and free of charge service from the European Commission addressing Research & Innovation projects. Led by the LandSense Citizen Observatory (CO), an innovative project group was formed with other H2020 COs including Ground Truth 2.0, GROW Observatory, Scent and WeObserve) aiming at demonstrating the societal and economic benefits of involving citizens in environmental decision-making and cooperative planning.

3.2.5 Earth Observation (Phi Week) at ESA-ESRIN in Frascati, Italy

12-16.11.2018

The Earth Observation (Phi Week) at ESA-ESRIN brought together various stakeholders across the private and public sector in a series of workshops, roundtables, and hackathons to share the latest trends in EO Open Science. Inian Moorthy (IIASA) presented the LandSense project during a dedicated Citizen Science session chaired by consortium partner Margaret Gold of the European Citizen Science Association. The presentation first provided a short overview of the demonstration cases, and then focused on our Engagement Platform and LandSense Federation. Emphasis on the Single-Sign-On

methodology and the GDPR compliance measures were noted and appreciated by the participants in follow-up discussions.

Video from the Citizen Science session can be accessed [here](#).

Interview with Margaret Gold (ECSA) is available [here](#).

3.2.6 Participation in Citizens Science Awards 2019

December 2018

Since 2015, the Austrian Ministry of Education, Science and Research together with Zentrum für Citizen Science are supporting Citizen science projects and science-oriented open innovation projects of Austrian research institutions with the aim to inspire citizens for research and to encourage active support. The LandSense project was chosen to take a part in the Citizen Science Award 2019 until mid-December 2019.

3.2.7 Mapathon organized by IGN, France

1.02.2019

30 students from ENSG (l'école de la géomatique) in Paris, participated in a mapathon organized by IGN (Institut national de l'information géographique et forestière) to validate urban changes identified by the Landsense Change Detection Service (CDS).

The LandSense CDS, which is developed and implemented by LandSense partner GeoVille Information Systems and Data Processing GmbH, provided near real-time high-quality land use and land cover (LULC) change detection information by using the power of the Copernicus Sentinel

missions.

The students were able to validate more than 600 detected changes, making the validation mapathon a big success. The validation was used to train and further develop the CDS algorithm and hence, to improve authoritative LULC data.

3.2.8 Launch of a new cycle of the LandSense pilot activities in Vojvodina, Serbia

February - March 2019

InoSense launched a series of LandSense Agricultural pilot activities in Vojvodina. First two activities were workshops in northern Serbian villages Srbobran and Selenca. Teaming up with farming associations, InoSense had successfully involved local farmers in citizen sciences, for collection of agricultural LULC data. Both events were well attended, resulting in over 25 farmers committed to provide their in-situ data for the 2019 season. It was agreed that farmers will use the CropSupport application to collect data from their fields and crops. As a compensation and stimulation for active

collection and sharing of the data, the farmers were offered several free services from CropSupport, such as parcel-level weather forecast and NDVI maps.

3.2.9 Annual European Geosciences Union – EGU Assembly, Vienna, Austria

12.04. 2019

During the poster session on 'bridging the science-society-gap by finding emerging environmental issues and empowering citizens' the LandSense team presented the CityOasesApp to the experts at this year's EGU Assembly.

Within the LandSense project this mobile application aims to stimulate civic engagement to monitor changes within the urban environment and to enable users to drive improvements by providing city planners with information about the public perception of urban spaces. The app had been set to officially launch during an open event on city development held by Vienna's Municipal Department 18 (MA 18 - Urban Development and Planning) in mid-May, but it was already available from May 2nd, when CityOases took part of the Austrian Citizen Science Award. This Award, which was backed by the Austrian Ministry of Education, Science and Research, supported research projects with the aim to inspire citizens for research and encouraged active support. Nearly 12.000 citizens had participated since the inaugural competition in 2015. The most enthusiastic citizen scientists have been awarded with prizes in a festive event by the ministry together with the research projects.

The conversations with our peers at the EGU Assembly were overwhelmingly positive with some users downloading and checking out the beta version on the spot or in nearby Donaustadt park, as well as questions about the app's availability in other cities and very positive feedback on the look and feel of the app.

3.2.10 GEO Data Technology Workshop: The Era of Big EO Data, Vienna, Austria

23-25.04.2019

(Photo source: www.earthobservations.org)

LandSense Coordinator Steffen Fritz was participating at the Group on Earth Observations Data Technology Workshop in Vienna discussing the needs, challenges, innovations and opportunities for Big Earth Observation data.

3.2.11 A 3-days stakeholder workshop in Labuan Bajo, Flores, Indonesia

April 2019

At the beginning of April 2019, Burung Indonesia and BirdLife International organized a 3-days stakeholder workshop in Labuan Bajo, Flores, Indonesia.

The main objectives of the workshop were to discuss upcoming opportunities for the monitoring of Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) and Important Bird and Biodiversity Areas (IBAs) in the area within the LandSense framework to have a better understanding of the conservation strategies developed and to find synergies for future work. Participants

included Local Conservation Group members, village authorities, Forest Management Unit, Community Empowerment Agency, Nature Conservation Agency, Environmental Agency and Development Planning Agency at Sub-National Level.

The first two days were used to discuss on how Natura Alert App can contribute to the value of community-based monitoring results. The participants were also able to try the Natura Alert App on their smart phone and gave their valuable feedback to the developers. Furthermore, business opportunities as well as potentials for local communities were identified. On the third day, ground truth validation was performed to verify the remote sensing result for the alerts system in the area. The workshop was very successful with active participation from all stakeholder and real hands-on experiences on conducting monitoring using technology for the users and successfully receiving feedbacks.

3.2.12 LandSense and CropSupport presentation at the Universität Würzburg, Germany

30.05.2019

INOSENS presented the LandSense projects and discussed potential exploitation of the CropSupport application with over 20 international researchers from a broad field of biodiversity protection and land mapping, which gathered at the Universität Würzburg.

3.2.13 Living Planet Symposium 2019, Milan, Italy

15.05.2019

The partners from Wageningen University & Research gave an oral presentation titled “Alert-Driven Participatory Forest Monitoring Using Sentinel Data and Mobile Phone Technology: Case Studies in Three Continents”. Here, the achievements of the prototype of the alerting system experimented on Flores Island in the scope of the LandSense project were presented.

3.2.14 International Brokerage Event “International Brokerage Event”, Istanbul, Turkey

5.07.2019

The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) with the support of the EU-funded project “Turkey in Horizon 2020 Phase II” organised “ICTurkey 2019”, International Brokerage Event in Istanbul on the 5th of July. The event brought more than 450 participants from both research and industrial communities involved in ICT research from the EU and Turkey.

INOSENS team discussed potential exploitation paths of the LandSense services with over 20 different stakeholders both from Turkey and the EU.

3.2.15 International Cartographic Conference in Tokyo, Japan

19.07.2019

Laurence Jolivet from IGN (Institut national de l'information géographique et forestière) presented the results of the Toulouse pilot campaign at International Cartographic Conference in Tokyo.

The abstract of the presentation titled “Feedbacks on VGI in-situ campaign for updating LULC data” could be accessed through this [link](#).

3.2.16 GeoCultGIS Workshop at the AGILE 2019 Conference in Limassol, Cyprus

July 2019

Together with colleagues, Michael Schultz from GIScience Heidelberg organized a pre-conference workshop as part of the AGILE 2019 conference in Limassol. The workshop titled “Geographical and Cultural Aspects of Geoinformation: Issues and Solutions (geoCultGIS)” aimed at developing a discussion around the constraints geo-cultural contexts put on the generalizability and transferability of geoinformatic methods and geographical data, while also considering the approaches for handling these.

3.2.17 “Forschungsfest” workshop at the Palais Niederösterreich, Vienna, Austria

September 2019

Exploring urban green spaces in Vienna and letting other people know where the best places are in the city. All this and much more was discussed during the “Forschungsfest” at the Palais Niederösterreich in Vienna last week.

The representatives from the Environmental Agency Austria (EAA) were excited to introduce the CityOases App as a tool to not only improve the database of open urban spaces and their usage, but also to find new ways to enjoy the city and make it more livable. People were eager to install the app and had the chance to test its functionalities in the areas around the palais. Further, the EAA team put the new CityOases Card game on display, which is entirely based on user feedback on the Viennese green spaces and hence, presents a real piece of innovative Citizens Science.

„The workshop has significantly contributed to raise awareness of the CityOases App among interested citizens” said Barbara Birli from EAA. “By providing a tool that empowers citizens, we can make use of their local knowledge and they have the chance to directly influence the green infrastructure of the city.”

3.2.18 Joint Event “Observing the Environment: Challenges and Opportunities in Citizen Science”, Brussels, Belgium

09.10.2019

The four Citizen Observatory (CO) projects launched in 2016 and funded by the EC H2020 (LandSense, GROW Observatory, Scent and Ground Truth 2.0) came together to showcase their achievements, share best practices, and discuss their impact and sustainability beyond the project lifecycle.

There had been discussion about important issues affecting COs, including key challenges, methodologies and tools, impact and sustainability, as well as future opportunities. Besides exchanging ideas and lessons learned, the outputs of this meeting fed into a report summarising obstacles and recommendations for future programs. The event addressed citizen science practitioners, people involved in planning, setting-up, or leading a CO.

3.2.19 Farmers Day, Novi Sad, Serbia

04.12.2019

INOSENS teamed up with the local farmer community to present achievements of LandSense's Agricultural Campaign 2019 activities. The LandSense project and its' CropSupport Services were presented, while the farmers were provided with feedback on their activities and value they created for the LandSense project.

3.2.20 INSPIRE Hackathon 2020, Dubrovnik, Croatia

May 2020

DUBROVNIK INSPIRE HACKATHON 2020

The INSPIRE Hackathon 2020 was in line with the motto of the INSPIRE Conference – “Bringing sustainability and digitalisation together”. The goal of the hackathon was to promote collaboration and sharing of experience in the domain of spatial data/services and citizen-science while showcasing their utilisation and uptake to different application domains

and themes. This includes supporting the Sustainable Developments Goals.

Despite the cancellation of the INSPIRE Conference 2020 in Dubrovnik, the Dubrovnik INSPIRE Hackathon 2020 continued as a fully virtual event. Andreas Matheus (Secure Dimensions), one of the LandSense team members, mentored the Hackathon.

3.2.21 Initiative related to the Covid-19 situation

May 2020

As a citizen science project, the LandSense team discussed with the representatives from the European Commission possible initiative related to the current Covid-19 situation and how to contribute within the project with apps and data to solve this challenging situation.

The LandSense partners discussed internally how the project will be aligned and contribute to the planned toolbox and support the recommendations of the commission related to COVID-19 situation.

3.2.22 ECSA Conference 2020, Trieste, Italy

6-10.09.2020

The LandSense partners participated at the conference and gave the following presentation: a) oral presentation: “Citizen science and personal data protection: the LandSense approach” (authors: Andreas Matheus, Inian Moorthy, Linda See, Matej Batic and Steffen Fritz); b) E-poster: “Natura Alert: monitoring biodiversity threats using citizen science” (authors: Sofia Capellan, Ivan Ramirez,

Linda See, Anto Subash, Inian Moorthy, Steffen Fritz, Octavio Infante and Lalu Abdi Wirastami); c) E-poster: “The LandSense Innovation Challenge” (authors: Vladimir Mrkajic, Nemanja Nicin, Matej Batič, Margaret Gold, Tim Woods, Inian Moorthy, Linda See and Steffen Fritz).

3.3 Intensification of the online ecosystem building activities as reaction to the COVID-19 situation

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic and associated lockdown in various countries caused the cancellation of all planned F2F LandSense ecosystem building activities – such as the second LandSense Innovation Challenge and participation in different events (conferences, hackathons, workshops, etc.). For the LandSense consortium, this was a challenging situation, as the project has entered its final stage where F2F activities were envisioned to ensure stakeholder engagement in exploiting LandSense results and providing feedback to the consortium. To overcome this challenge, the team has focused on an intensive online presence on social media channels, nourishing and expanding an ecosystem of stakeholders who support further uptake and exploitation of the project results. In particular, the LandSense team has been very active in disseminating the project results and outcomes as well as in engaging the stakeholders in dozens of the most active and populated FaceBook groups related to EO and Citizen Science. The following most populated and active online communities where the LandSense related news and topics have been discussed are:

EO community

Geoscience, Remote Sensing and GIS Community
19K members • 20 posts a day

QGIS community
35K members • 40 posts a day

GIS and RS Techniques
18K members • 30 posts a day

Remote sensing & GIS RGSC BHU
17K members • 20 posts a day

Remote Sensing and GIS Technology
51K members • 100 posts a day

Remote Sensing & GIS
38K members • 20 posts a day

GIS (geographic Info Sys)
25K members • 8 posts a day

Google Earth Engine
17K members • 30 posts a day

Applied Remote Sensing and GIS
23K members • 9 posts a day

Geospatial analysis
21K members • 50 posts a day

Biodiversity Informatics Training Curriculum
8.5K members • 40 posts a day

Geoscience and Remote Sensing
51K members • 20 posts a day

Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation (ITC)
14K members • 5 posts a day

Citizen Science community

Citizen Science & Constantly Curious Community
22K members • 3 posts a day

Citizen Science for Systemic Change
198 members • 4 posts a week

Citizen Science
1.3K members • 2 posts a day

4. Future activities and concluding remarks

The upcoming activities focus on further inclusion of different EO and Citizen Science actors within the existing LandSense ecosystem, but also towards providing them with the knowledge to use LandSense services, data streams and all other outcomes. Also, the LandSense team will continue to provide business and technical support to the Challenge winners to further develop and marketize their solutions. This might lead to joint exploitation activities among the winners and some of the LandSense partners. As described in this deliverable, the consortium has been very active in building the LandSense ecosystem of actors during the second half of the project. The shared defining characteristics of all partners has been the long-term and system-wide approach in engaging relevant EO stakeholders and citizens in project activities, ultimately contributing to the overall EO value chain maturity and the uptake and dissemination of LandSense services. Finally, all efforts invested in creating a valuable ecosystem of stakeholders who support further uptake of the project results will lead to stronger post project exploitation and commercialization capabilities.

5. Annex

5.1 Second LandSense Innovation Challenge Call

LandSense
 A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
 for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Call for Proposals LandSense Online Innovation Challenge Data-driven solutions for environmental monitoring

About LandSense

[LandSense](#) is building an innovative citizen observatory to uncover the collective potential of citizen-powered science and satellite imagery to improve the way we see, map and understand the world.

The LandSense Citizen Observatory, funded by the Horizon 2020 program, will offer modern community-based environmental monitoring tools and information systems to help transform decision making. Through **Earth Observation (EO)-driven** mobile applications, LandSense promotes citizens to not only play a key role in environmental monitoring, but also to be directly involved in the co-creation of such applications. Currently within the EU's EO monitoring framework, especially in the domain of Land Use Land Cover (LULC) dynamics, there is a need for low-cost methods for acquiring high quality in-situ data to create timely, accurate and well-validated environmental monitoring products. LandSense aims to disrupt the EO data economy by creating marketable solutions that can provide a step-change in LULC monitoring activities both within and beyond Europe.

About the LandSense Online Innovation Challenge

The Challenge targets individuals, web-entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs coming from all [participating Horizon 2020 countries](#), to present innovative IT solutions addressing one of the three LandSense domains: **Urban Landscape Dynamics, Agricultural Land Use, and Forest & Habitat Monitoring**. The challenge focuses on using **data streams coming from the LandSense Citizen Observatory, the Sentinel Hub Service or other relevant EO data sources** to design novel LULC solutions for a range of applications within the selected domains.

Selected LandSense Challenge finalists will have the opportunity to pitch their ideas online to an expert jury at a side event on September 11, 2020 following the [Third International ECSA Online Conference 2020](#). The participation in the online public challenge is fully free of charge.

Each of the finalists will receive:

- Business coaching on how to pitch the idea before the challenge via a webinar
- Promotional services of the LandSense project

The teams with the best pitches will receive:

1st prize

- A grand prize of 2,000 EUR
- A 1-year subscription to Sentinel Hub Enterprise, worth 5,000 EUR, provided by SINERGISE
- Online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the LandSense team

2nd prize

- A prize of 1,000 EUR
- Online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the LandSense team

3rd prize

- A prize of 500 EUR
- Online business coaching and mentorship services provided by the LandSense team

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 689812

Challenge Concept

The LandSense Innovation Challenge supports knowledge sharing through a one-day event where participants can **present and share their technical capabilities, research and creativity**.

The objectives of the **LandSense Innovation Challenge** are to:

- i) **Promote the best pitch presentations** that could have a **clear business impact**
- ii) **Stimulate the collective power of citizen science and earth observation for environmental monitoring**
- iii) **Create awareness about the LandSense project objectives and outcomes**
- iv) **Foster the community spirit within the LandSense Citizen Observatory**

About the Third International ECSA Conference 2020

The Challenge will take place on September 11, 2020 in conjunction with the [Third International ECSA Online Conference 2020](#) (Sep 6-10, 2020). This conference is aimed at scientists, practitioners, activists, funders, policy makers in the field of citizen science, non-governmental organizations, artists, and interested citizens. Themes within the conference include a) the current state and future direction of citizen science, b) inclusiveness, equity and empowerment in citizen science, and c) technology-mediated citizen science among many other related topics.

About Sentinel Hub

Sentinel Hub's trial accounts will be opened for all participants during the first stage of the challenge and will be extended for the finalists during the final Challenge. To apply for the trial account, click [here](#).

Sentinel Hub is a Copernicus Masters award winning service for cloud-based storage, processing and distribution of satellite imagery. It targets application developers and remote sensing experts to side-step work-intensive and costly basic data processing so they can focus on creating added value services for end-users. Sentinel Hub provides seamless and immediate access to the full worldwide archive of Copernicus Sentinel satellites (Sentinel 1, 2 and 3) as well as other sources such as Landsat 5, 7, 8, Envisat Meris and others. Services provide access to more than 2 PB of data and at this moment process more than one million requests each day, coming from users around the world, either using one of Sentinel Hub's free applications ([Sentinel Playground](#), [EO Browser](#)) or, more importantly, one of the 3rd party applications, which are powered by Sentinel Hub services. More information can be found at [Sentinel Hub](#).

How to Apply for the LandSense Challenge?

The LandSense Challenge is dedicated to facilitating the development of innovative IT applications that are addressing the field of LULC within one of three LandSense domains:

1. **Urban Landscape Dynamics** - This theme focuses on engaging citizens in monitoring land change in urban and peri-urban areas. Solutions should be oriented towards local decision makers to support urban monitoring and planning.
2. **Agricultural Land Use** - This theme focuses on leveraging the power of EO systems and advanced crowdsourcing techniques to deliver value-added services to European farmers and public authorities involved in the agricultural sector.
3. **Forest & Habitat Monitoring** – Solutions within these domains should support in situ data collection to help monitor protected areas such as wildlife reserves, conservation areas, and other biodiversity hotspots.

The process is divided into **two stages**:

The first stage calls for ideas and invites participants to **submit proposals for IT-based LULC solutions within one of three LandSense domains**. Proposals (up to 3 pages long) should be submitted to the LandSense team by Friday 21 August 2020 (5pm CET), using the following email address: challenge@landsense.eu. Please see the **LandSense Challenge Application Form** for further details. Although not mandatory, participants are highly encouraged to exploit the various open LandSense datasets, provided as part of the challenge, in their proposals. **Datasets are available via <https://landsense.eu/Challenge>**.

All individuals interested are encouraged to register to stay informed about the challenge and related webinars.

The **second stage** includes up to **10 best proposals** to be selected by the LandSense expert jury, where the finalists will be announced on *Monday, 31 August 2020 (5pm CET)*. The applicants will then have over a week to finalize and further develop their solutions, demos/mock-ups, and pitch presentations to present to the jury at the LandSense Challenge Finals on September 11, 2020. Prior to the finals, the LandSense team will organize a coaching webinar on “How to pitch your idea” to help guide participants.

Please note that registration for the ECSA Conference is not required for participation in this public challenge.

**If the applicants subscribe to the Sentinel Hub trial account, they are requested to inform the LandSense Team, by emailing challenge@landsense.eu the email address that they have used in the registration process, so the trial account can be extended throughout first stage of the Challenge period. The Sentinel Hub trial account will be extended after the first stage for finalists only and will be open until the end of the Challenge.*

Selection Criteria

The LandSense expert jury will assess the submitted proposals based on the following selection criteria. Criteria and thresholds apply to both the first and second stage of the proposal.

Selection Criteria	Points	Threshold
Feasibility of the concept	1-5	4
Market potential	1-5	4
Relevance for the domain	1-5	4
		Total: max. 15

Detailed description of the selection criteria

Applicants should pay attention to the following criteria when devising their idea and preparing the application.

Feasibility of the concept:

- i) Is the concept relevant to the field of LULC monitoring?
- ii) Are objectives well described (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time-bound)?
- iii) Is the proposed technical approach sound and appropriate for the scope of the proposal?

Market potential:

- i) Have you clearly identified the target market (size, segments, etc.)?
- ii) Do you clearly describe positioning and unique selling points?
- iii) Do you have a sound market penetration strategy?
- iv) Do you have an appropriate business and growth model in place?

Relevance for the domain:

- i) How applicable and scalable is your solution for addressing challenges within the domain?
- ii) How might future environmental management and public participation impact from using your solution?
- iii) How can the new Citizens’ Observatories as well as next generations of observatories re-use and tailor your solution?

Contact and Important Dates

For more detailed information: <https://landsense.eu/challenge>
 More questions? Please contact: challenge@landsense.eu
 About Sentinel hub: <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>

Deadline for submission of proposals: *Friday 21 August 2020, 17:00 CET*
 Invitation of selected finalists: *Monday 31 August 2020, 17:00 CET*
 Online Challenge event: *Friday 11 September 2020*

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 689812

5.2 Second LandSense Innovation Challenge Application Form

LandSense
A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

LandSense Online Innovation Challenge

**Data-driven solutions for environmental
monitoring**

Application Form

To submit an idea for the LandSense Challenge, you need to prepare a short description that should be sent by e-mail as a PDF file to the following address: challenge@landsense.eu

Please use the following subject: LandSense Innovation Challenge Application

Format

Please prepare your proposal as a PDF file no longer than 3 pages plus a title page. You can optionally add 1 page with a figure, presenting your software application's architecture. Each file must not be larger than 10 MB.

Title Page

Please include the following information on the title page:

- Title of the challenge: LandSense Challenge
- Title of your proposal/idea
- Name and webpage of your organisation if applicable
- Name, email, telephone number, address of the contact person
- Date of preparation and/or version number

Content of Your Proposal

The body of your proposal should include the following parts and must not exceed 3 pages:

- Short description/abstract of your idea, clearly outlining the key elements (maximum 200 words)
- Outline the problem that you are planning to address
- Describe your envisaged solution and the key benefits/impacts
- Targeted market – foreseen customers and market size
- Roughly outline your business model
- Explain which technology you are planning to use
- Short descriptions of key personnel in the team

Use the most appropriate means to present your idea, i.e. as text, tables, graphical explanations, etc.

You may also add 1 additional page that provides a graphical overview of your envisaged software application's architecture, which will identify the main components of your solution.

Important Dates:

Submission of proposals: **Friday 21 August 2020, 17:00 CET**

Announcement of selected finalists: **Monday 31 August 2020, 17:00 CET**

The Online Challenge Event: **Friday 11 September 2020**

Proposal for the LandSense Challenge

Title:
<Title of your proposal/idea>

Organisation Name: if applicable

Webpage: if applicable

Contact Person:
Name
Email
Telephone number
Address

Have you used Sentinel Hub in your idea Yes No **If not, please specify what data you have used:**

Date:

Version:

Content of Your Proposal (max 3 pages)

The body of your proposal should include the following parts and must not exceed 2 pages. You are free to use text, tables or graphical explanations.

1. Relevance for the domain

The Idea (maximum 200 words)

Short description/abstract of your idea, clearly outlining the key elements.

The Problem

Outline the problem that you are planning to address

Envisaged Solution and Benefits

Explain your envisaged solution and the key benefits compared to the current situation.

Innovation

In one sentence, outline how your idea is innovative.

2. Feasibility of the concept

Business Model

Roughly outline your business model including positioning, unique selling points, and the future growth model.

Technology used

Explain the technologies you are planning to use

The Team

Briefly describe your team

3. Market potential

Market

Who is your target market, i.e. the rough size, potential customers and market penetration strategy?

Architecture of the Software Application (Optional and max 1 page)

If you consider it useful, you can add 1 additional page to add an illustration of your software/hardware architecture, which will identify the main components of your solution.

5.3 Second LandSense Innovation Challenge Agenda

LandSense Innovation Challenge

Data-driven solutions for environmental monitoring

AGENDA

Date: 11 September 2020

Time: 13-16h (Central Summer European Time)

Connection link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85841664950?pwd=SXc0UnlKYUhyZ1Z1ajlnUEpmbXVnUT09>

Part 1 – PLENARY SESSION		
Topic	Presenter	Timing
LandSense: A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring	Inian Moorthy (International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis - IIASA, Austria)	13:00-13:20
A brief tour of the landscape of Citizen Science and Citizen Observatories	Margaret Gold (European Citizen Science Association - ECSA)	13:20-13:35
Earth Observation for everyone - linking citizen science with Sentinel Hub services	Matej Batič (SINERGISE, Slovenia)	13:35-13:50
Break (10 minutes)		
Part 2 - PITCH PRESENTATIONS (10 minute per pitch + 10 minute for discussion)		
iShow Tenure - iST	Ali Freeman, Zimbabwe	14:00-14:20
iObserve app for Forest and Habitat Monitoring	Ravindhiran Viswalingam, France	14:20-14:40
A satellite imagery-based mapping prototype for land use mapping by land users	Marcos Moreu, UK	14:40-15:00
Break (10 minutes)		
Geospatial platform for allergenic plant monitoring and management	Minučer Mesaroš, Serbia	15:10-15:30
Monitoring of Community Forestry on Bio-Physical parameters through Geospatial approach	Him Lal Shrestha, Nepal	15:30-15:50
PART 3: EVENT CLOSING		
Closing remarks	Inian Moorthy	15:50-16:00

Challenge winners will be notified by email on Monday 14 September

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 689812

5.4 Second LandSense Challenge Survey

Feedback on the LandSense Innovation Challenge

Please submit feedback regarding the event you have participate.

*** Required**

1. Pre-event organization was done diligently and efficiently *

excellent

good

weak

bad

2. Speakers were interesting and informing *

excellent

good

weak

bad

Overall organization of the LS Challenge Finals was well prepared *

- excellent
- good
- weak
- bad

4. Will you attend future LandSense Events *

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree

5. Will you further develop your idea? *

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree